

PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract:

This article explores the importance of the art of critical thinking in the field of English language teaching and learning. It discusses how critical thinking contributes to the development of analysis, evaluation, and argumentation skills, which are integral to effective English language use. The article presents strategies and methods that can be employed by educators to stimulate critical thinking among students in the process of learning English. It also emphasizes the significance of creating an environment that encourages students to engage in independent thinking, text analysis, and critical discussions within the context of English language learning. Lastly, the article demonstrates how the application of critical thinking in the educational process facilitates the development of communicative skills in the English language and improves the quality of education.

Аннотация:

Эта статья исследует важность искусства критического мышления в области обучения и изучения английского языка. Она обсуждает, как критическое мышление способствует развитию навыков анализа, оценки и аргументации, которые являются неотъемлемой частью эффективного использования английского языка. Статья предлагает стратегии и методы, которые могут быть использованы педагогами для стимулирования критического мышления среди студентов в процессе изучения английского языка. Также подчеркивается значимость создания среды, которая поощряет студентов к независимому мышлению, анализу текстов и критическим обсуждениям в контексте изучения английского языка. Статья демонстрирует, как применение критического мышления в образовательном процессе способствует развитию коммуникативных навыков на английском языке и улучшает качество образования.

Anotatsiya:

Bu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitish va o'rganish sohasida tanqidiy fikrlash san'ati muhimligini o'rganadi. U tanqidiy fikrlashning tahlil, baholash va dalillash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini muhokama qiladi, bu ko'nikmalar ingliz tilidan samarali foydalanishning ajralmas qismidir. Maqola ta'lim beruvchilar tomonidan ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayonida o'quvchilar orasida tanqidiy fikrlashni rag'batlantirish uchun qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan strategiya va usullarni taqdim etadi. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarni mustaqil fikrlashga, matn tahliliga va ingliz tilini o'rganish kontekstida tanqidiy muhokamalarga jalb qiladigan muhit yaratishning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi. Maqolada ta'lim jarayonida tanqidiy fikrlashning qo'llanilishi ingliz tilida muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga va ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga qanday yordam berishini ko'rsatiladi.

Keywords: critical thinking, learning English, reading skills, effective communication, problem-solving, cultural understanding, strategies, methods, educators, pupils.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, изучение английского языка, навыки чтения, эффективная коммуникация, решение проблем, культурное понимание, стратегии, методы, педагоги, учащиеся.

Kalit so‘zlar : tanqidiy fikrlash, ingliz tilini o‘rganish, o‘qish ko‘nikmalari, samarali kommunikatsiya, muammo yechish, madaniy tushuncha, strategiyalar, usullar, o‘qituvchilar, o‘quvchilar.

Critical thinking is an essential skill in modern education, and its significance in the field of English language teaching and learning is increasingly gaining attention. In the era of the information society, where access to knowledge and information has become more extensive, the ability to think critically has become a key factor in successfully using the English language. In the context of English language teaching and learning, critical thinking involves students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and articulate information in English. This skill enables students not only to comprehend texts and materials in the English language but also to think critically about them, express their ideas and viewpoints, and make informed decisions based on the analysis of available information. In this article, we will discuss the importance of the art of critical thinking in the field of English language teaching and learning. We will explore how critical thinking contributes to the development of analytical, evaluative, and argumentative skills, which are integral to the effective use of the English language. Additionally, we will present strategies and methods that can be employed by educators to promote critical thinking among students in the process of learning English.

It is crucial to create an environment that encourages students to engage in independent thinking, textual analysis, and critical discussions, as well as fosters the development of communicative skills in the English language. We will also examine the impact of incorporating critical thinking in the educational process on enhancing the quality of learning and the development of communicative skills in English. Ultimately, understanding and applying critical thinking in the context of English language teaching and learning hold significant value for students, as it helps them develop analytical, evaluative, and argumentative skills, as well as effectively utilize the English language in various spheres of life and work.

Strategies and teaching methods can be used to stimulate critical thinking among students in the process of learning the English language. Here are some of them [1]:

- Questioning approach: Foster interactive discussions where students ask and answer questions, as well as discuss ideas and arguments. Encourage their critical thinking by asking open-ended questions that require analysis and reasoned responses. This helps develop their skills in analysis, evaluation, and argumentation in English.

- Group work: Organize group projects or assignments where students have to collaborate and exchange ideas. This stimulates critical thinking as students need to analyze information, develop arguments, and make collective decisions in English. Group work also develops communication and teamwork skills.

- Contextual tasks: Provide students with real-life situations or problems that require analysis and solution. For example, you can have them read an article in

English about a social issue and ask them to express their opinion and propose solutions. This helps develop their skills in analysis, evaluation, and critical thinking.

- Development of critical reading skills: Teach students strategies for active reading, such as scanning, skimming, and critical reading. This will help them develop skills in analyzing English texts, identifying key ideas, evaluating arguments, and expressing their opinions.

- Support for constructive criticism: Encourage students to provide constructive criticism and argue their points of view. Teach them ways to express different perspectives and arguments in written and oral form in English. This helps them develop argumentative skills and confidence in expressing their ideas.

- Use of information sources: Teach students how to search, select, and evaluate information sources in English. This includes critically assessing sources, verifying their reliability, and analyzing the information they provide. This helps students develop critical thinking and literacy in English.

- Development of argumentation skills: Teach students logical methods of argumentation and developing their ideas in written and oral form. Encourage their critical thinking by asking open-ended questions and demanding reasoned answers, so they can develop their argumentative skills and the ability to express their thoughts clearly and logically in English.

It is important to remember that stimulating critical thinking requires a systematic approach and consistent practice. Teachers should create a stimulating learning environment where students can freely express their opinions, argue their ideas, and ask questions. They should also provide feedback and support for the development of critical thinking skills among students. Creating an environment that supports the development of critical thinking skills in students is an important aspect of effective education. Here are some detailed recommendations for creating such an environment[2]:

- Setting goals: Define specific goals related to the development of critical thinking and clearly explain them to the students. Emphasize the importance of developing analytical and evaluative skills in the process of learning the English language.

- Supporting open discussion: Create an atmosphere where students can freely express their thoughts and ideas. Encourage them to ask questions, express different points of view, and discuss issues and topics in English. Stimulate argumentation and debates so that students can learn to think critically and articulate their views.

- Providing diverse materials: Provide students with diverse sources of information in English, such as texts, articles, videos, audio recordings, etc. This will help them develop skills in analyzing and evaluating information, as well as enrich their knowledge and understanding of various topics.

- Posing open-ended questions: Incorporate open-ended questions into your lessons that require students to analyze, evaluate, and provide reasoned answers. This helps develop their critical thinking skills and ability to express their thoughts in English. Encourage students to ask each other questions and engage in discussions so they can learn to listen and argue their viewpoints.

- Organizing group work: Give students opportunities to work in groups where they can collaborate, exchange ideas, and solve problems. Group work fosters the development of critical thinking as students must analyze information, develop arguments, and make collective decisions in English. It's important to ensure equal participation of all members and create structured tasks that require critical thinking.

- Encouraging reflection: After completing assignments or projects, allow students to reflect on their achievements and mistakes. Ask questions about what they have learned, what challenges they encountered, and how they can improve their critical thinking skills. Encourage students to think about their thinking processes and develop strategies for enhancing their skills.

- Feedback and support: Provide students with constructive feedback on their work and thoughts. Pay attention to the development of their argumentation skills and their ability to express their thoughts clearly and logically in English. Encourage their critical thinking and offer strategies for improvement.

- Utilizing technology: Use technology such as interactive online resources, educational apps, and social networks to support students' critical thinking. This can include assignments utilizing interactive tools, discussions on virtual forums, or collaborative creation of digital projects. Technology can expand students' opportunities for research, analysis, and idea exchange in English.

Critical thinking has a significant impact on communicative skills in the English language. Here are some ways in which the development of critical thinking can influence communicative skills[3]:

- Analysis and understanding of information: Critical thinking helps students develop the skill of analyzing information in the English language. They become more critically aware of what they hear and read and are able to assess the accuracy and relevance of information. This enables them to better understand and interpret communicative materials in English.

- Development of argumentation and logical thinking: Critical thinking requires the development of the ability to articulate ideas and opinions. Students who master critical thinking learn to clarify their thoughts, construct logical chains of reasoning, and express their arguments more convincingly in English. This contributes to the development of effective communication skills.

- Development of critical reading and listening skills: Critical thinking helps students become more attentive listeners and readers in the English language. They learn to analyze and evaluate information, seek hidden meanings, identify key arguments, and distinguish facts from opinions. This allows them to better understand and comprehend communication in English.

- Development of critical writing and speaking skills: Critical thinking helps students become more effective writers and speakers in the English language. They learn to analyze and evaluate information, structure their thoughts, use arguments and evidence to support their ideas. This contributes to the development of critical writing and speaking skills in English.

- Development of empathy and respect for diverse opinions: Critical thinking also contributes to the development of empathy and respect for diverse opinions.

Students possessing this skill learn to listen attentively and consider other people's points of view in English. They learn to ask questions and engage in dialogue with politeness and tolerance, which promotes effective communication.

•The development of critical thinking and communicative skills in the English language is interconnected and mutually enriching. By developing critical thinking, students become more competent communicators in English, which in turn promotes the development of critical thinking. These skills are essential for successful communication in various areas of life, including academic, professional, and social spheres.

In conclusion, the application of critical thinking in learning the English language is of great importance and can bring numerous benefits to students. The development of critical thinking enables them to analyze and evaluate information, structure their thoughts, present arguments, and consider diverse opinions. This contributes to the development of effective communication skills in English, which are essential for academic, professional, and everyday interactions. The application of critical thinking also helps students better understand and interpret communicative materials in the English language, whether they are texts, speeches, or dialogues. They become attentive listeners and readers, capable of analyzing information, distinguishing facts from opinions, and identifying key arguments. This allows them to delve deeper into the meaning of communication and interact effectively with others in English. Furthermore, the development of critical thinking fosters empathy and respect for diverse opinions [4]. Students learn to acknowledge and consider other people's perspectives, ask questions, and engage in dialogue with respect and tolerance. This creates a conducive atmosphere for interaction and promotes constructive exchange of ideas and information in the English language. Overall, the development of critical thinking is an integral part of learning the English language. It not only contributes to the development of communicative skills but also cultivates skills in analysis, logical thinking, empathy, and respect for diverse opinions. These skills are not only valuable in academic and professional domains but also help students become critical thinkers and informed citizens in a world where communication in English plays an increasingly important role.

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